

0001725

97502

POLISH

JOURNAL OF ENVIRONMENTAL
STUDIES

HARD OLSZTYN

**Vol. 15, No. 2B, 2006,
Part III**

Nutrition of Young Women

E. Stasiak, R. Domżał-Drzewicka, A. Stanisławek

Chair of Social Health Care, Nursing and Health Sciences Faculty,
Medical University of Lublin, Chodźki 6, 20-093 Lublin, Poland

Abstract

The homeostasis of the human organism depends on appropriate proportions of individual nutritional elements. After digestion and absorption these elements are used by the organism as a source of energy, construction material and factors controlling processes of life. Inadequate nutrition is one of serious dangers which human health is exposed to. Dietary habits are the basic element of healthy life style. They guarantee maintaining of good health condition, both physical and emotional one. Standardization of dietary habits of populations of economically developed countries (including Poland) is the basis for prophylactic activities which will bring substantial health benefits. The aim of this study was to examine the dietary habits of healthy, young women. There were described and analyzed dietary habits of young women who were under health care of family health nurses in Lubelskie Voivodship. The analysis of nutrition of 250 women was performed on the basis of the assessment of selected dietary habits and frequency of consumption of certain groups of food products. The respondents were also asked to make a self-assessment of their diets and possibly give reasons for their injudicious nutritional choices. It was revealed that certain aspects of the dietary habits of the studied group differed from the principles of rational nutrition. Over 42% of the surveyed women considered their nutrition styles appropriate, and mentioned insufficient knowledge of rational nutrition principles to be the main reason for their unhealthy nutrition.

Keywords: nutrition, young women, health

Introduction

It is undeniable that maintaining health is conditional on appropriate nutrition. The homeostasis of the human organism depends on appropriate proportions of individual nutritional elements. After digestion and absorption these elements are used by the organism as a source of energy, construction material and agents controlling vital processes [1, 2, 6].

Inadequate nutrition is one of serious dangers which human health is exposed to. Dietary habits are the basic element of healthy lifestyle. They guarantee maintaining of good health condition, both physical and emotional one. Standardization of dietary habits of populations of economically developed countries (including Poland) is the basis for prophylactic activities which will bring substantial health benefits [3, 4].

Dietary mistakes and inappropriate nutritional behaviours predispose to the development of a series of diseases

which are referred to as civilization-related diseases, *i.e.* diabetes, arterial hypertension, myocardial ischaemia or osteoporosis [5].

The aim of this study was to examine the dietary habits of healthy, young women.

Material and Methods

There were described and analyzed dietary habits of young women who were under health care of family health nurses in Lubelskie Voivodship.

The analysis of nutrition styles of 250 women was performed on the basis of the assessment of selected dietary habits: number and regularity of consumed meals and the frequency of consumption of certain groups of food products. The respondents were also asked to make a self-assessment of their nutrition styles and possibly give reasons for their injudicious dietary choices.

Results and Discussion

The majority of the female respondents stated that they had fewer than 3 meals a day (47.30%). Only 32.4% of the respondents declared having breakfast every day. Supper appears to be the most regularly

Table 1. Percentages of women declaring selected nutritional behaviours.

No.	Nutritional Behaviours	N	%
Daily number of meals:			
1.	3 meals	101	40.4
	4-5 meals	23	9.2
	fewer than 3 meals	122	48.8
	6 and more meals	4	1.6
Everyday consumption of main meals:			
2.	breakfast	81	32.4
	dinner	165	66
	supper	208	83.2
Supper time:			
3.	between 17.00 and 18.00 hrs	37	14.8
	between 18.00 and 19.00 hrs	85	34
	after 20.00 hrs	115	46
4.	Declared, regular 'having snacks' between meals	167	66.8
Products used to prepare meals:			
5.	packet, tinned	58	23.2
	jarred and frozen	100	40
	fresh products	92	36.8

Table 2. Groups of most frequently eaten food products.

Groups of most frequently eaten food products	Every day		2-3 times a week		Very rarely	
	N	%	N	%	N	%
Cereal products	250	100	-	-	-	-
white bread	174	69.6				
wholemeal bread	76	30.4				
Milk and dairy products	72	28.8	129	51.6	57	22.8
Meat and its products, fish, eggs	142	56.8	105	42	11	4.4
Fish	-	-	78	31.2	172	68.8
Vegetables, fruit, potatoes	100	40	150	60	-	-
Butter, sour cream, animal fats	1	0.4	71	28.4	176	69.7
Other kinds of fat	142	56.1	99	36	12	4.8
Sugar and confectionery	130	52	115	46	4	1.6

consumed meal, which was confirmed by more than 83% of the respondents. The largest group of the respondents mentioned 20:00 hrs to be their usual supper time. It should be noted that over 66% of the respondents confessed to "having snacks" between the main meals.

More than a half of the women prepare meals from available ready-made components or use ready-made dishes, *i.e.* so-called "packet, jarred or frozen foods" (Table 1).

The daily diets of all the respondents (100%) is based on highly processed cereal products. More than a half of the young women declare that they include meat and its products, eggs, sugar, confectionery and non-animal fats in their daily diets. 40% of the respondents admit to eating fruit and vegetables, including potatoes, every day. Milk and dairy products constitute only about 28% of a daily diet. It should be emphasized here, that almost 23% of the respondents drink milk or eat dairy products very rarely (Table 2).

Studies conducted in the last few years show that dairy product consumption tends to decrease, which also means low consumption of calcium and riboflavin, especially among the young population of our country. This fact is a risk factor for numerous diseases including osteoporosis [5, 6].

There has been observed inappropriate structure of carbohydrate consumption and changes in the consumption of fatty acids. Over 50% of the respondents claim to eat large amounts of monosaccharides in their daily diets, and use various plant fats in meal preparation. Meat and its products still constitute the foundations of a daily diet, and fish is quite rarely found in a young woman's diet.

Among the respondents over 42% of the women consider their nutrition styles proper (healthy), and indicate ignorance about healthy nutrition principles to be the main cause of their unhealthy diets (Figs. 1, 2).

Fig. 1. Respondents' opinions on their nutrition styles.

Fig. 2. Reasons for unhealthy nutrition styles.

Conclusions

1. Nutritional behaviours of the studied group differ from the principles of rational nutrition. The most frequent nutritional mistakes are related to both quality and amounts of consumed food.

2. Low consumption of dairy products, fish and wholemeal bread, which coincides with increased consumption of monosaccharides (mainly in the form of confectionery and sweets), meat and its products indicate the need for devising remedial action.
3. Most of the surveyed women consider their nutrition styles unhealthy and blame that situation on ignorance about the principles of healthy nutrition.
4. The results of the study indicate the necessity of providing health education, with a special focus on propagating the principles of healthy nutrition in different periods of human life.

References

1. HAŁATZ, KOZŁOWSKA-WOJCIECHOWSKAM., MAN-CARZ A., WRONKOWSKI Z.: Dieta dla zdrowia. Mag. Piel. Położ., 5, ss.42-43. 1997.
2. JAROSZ A.: Żywnienie a magnez. Now. Klin.1, ss. 60-64. 1944.
3. JEŻEWSKA-ZYCHOWICZ M.: Żywność i żywienie w kontekście potrzeb społecznych człowieka. Żyw. Człow. Metabol., XXIX, 4, ss. 251-258. 2002.
4. WORLD HEALTH ORGANISATION: Diet, nutrition and prevention of chronic disease, Report of joint WHO/FAO Expert Consultation. Technical Report Series, No 916, Geneva 2003.
5. PRZYSTAWSKI J., GERTIG H.: Żywnościowe czynniki rozwoju niektórych chorób cywilizacyjnych. Żyw. Człow. Metabol., 3, ss.354-366.1997.
6. ZIEMLAŃSKI Ś.: Normy żywienia człowieka, fizjologiczne podstawy. Wyd. Lek. PZWL, Warszawa 2001.